

Fluoborates. Part I. Physico-Chemical Studies on the Formation of Fluoborates

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From conductometric and thermometric titrations of the systems, $\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3\text{--KF}$, $\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3\text{--HF}$ and $\text{KBO}_2\text{--H}_2\text{O--HF}$, the existence of $\text{BF}(\text{OH})_3^-$, $\text{BF}_3(\text{OH})^-$ and BF_4^- ions have been shown. The existence of $\text{KBF}(\text{OH})_3$ has been proved through the phase rule study of the system $\text{KF--H}_3\text{BO}_3\text{--H}_2\text{O}$.

A survey in literature¹ shows that under suitable experimental conditions by reaction of boric acid with hydrofluoric acid HBF_4 , $\text{HBF}_3(\text{OH})$ and $\text{HBF}_2(\text{OH})_2$ can be isolated. The first systematic study of the $\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3\text{--HF}$ system was made by Wamser². From immediate conductivity measurements of the resulting solution obtained by mixing boric acid with hydrofluoric acid he showed that the two react instantaneously to give monohydroxy-trifluoroboric acid.

Recently from phase rule studies Pawlenko³ has confirmed the formation of the various fluoboric acids mentioned above, and has shown the existence of several hydrates of those acids. The existence of trihydroxymonofluoroboric acid or the anion, $\text{BF}(\text{OH})_3^-$, has, however, not shown by him.

Ryss and Slutskaya⁴ studied phase equilibria of the systems, (i) $\text{NaF--H}_3\text{BO}_3\text{--H}_2\text{O}$ and (ii) $\text{NaF--Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7\text{--H}_2\text{O}$. They reported a complex formation only in the former case.

The present authors have investigated the formation of trihydroxymonofluoroborate ion along with other fluoboric acids.

EXPERIMENTAL

For the conductometric titrations individual mixtures for each point were prepared in polythene bottles keeping the total volume constant. Blank solutions were also prepared in a similar manner. The solutions were allowed to stand for two weeks and the conductances were measured with dip type platinised platinum electrodes fitted into polythene tubes and using a polythene container. The conductance of the solutions were recorded with a Philips' conductivity measuring apparatus, Type PR-9500. The results of titration of (i) boric acid by potassium fluoride and (ii) of boric acid by hydrofluoric acid have been represented respectively in Figs. 1 and 2. The differences of the conductances observed in the titration of $\text{KBO}_2\text{--H}_2\text{O}$ by hydrofluoric acid and the sum of the conductances observed in the corresponding blank titrations were plotted (Fig. 3) against the mole ratio $\text{HF/KBO}_2\text{--H}_2\text{O}$.

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3. S. Pawlenko, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1962, **315**, 155.
4. I. G. Ryss and M. M. Slutskaya, *Izvest. Sektora. Platiny*.
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Fig. 1. Curve I, 10 ml boric acid (0.4159 *M*) was titrated by KF (1.308 *M*) having a total volume of the mixture 30 ml.
Curve II, 10 ml H_3BO_3 solution (0.4159 *M*) was titrated by KF (1.308 *M*) having a total volume of the mixture 30 ml.

Fig. 2. Curve I, 10 ml boric acid (0.1668 *M*) was titrated by HF (0.3077 *M*), having a total volume of the mixture 50 ml.
Curve II, 10 ml boric acid (0.1096 *M*) was titrated by HF (0.1371 *M*), having a total volume of the mixture 50 ml.
Curve Ia, represents the blank titration of HF (0.3077 *M*) with water, having a total volume 50 ml.

Fig. 3. Curve I, the differences of the conductances observed in the titration of 10 ml $KBO_2 \cdot H_2O$ solution (0.1594 M) by HF (0.116 M). (Total volume of the mixture 80 ml), and sum of the conductances in the blank titrations against mole ratio HF/ KBO_2 .
 Curve II, represent similar titrations of 10 ml $KBO_2 \cdot H_2O$ (0.09893 M) by HF (0.1936 M) in identical conditions. Total volume of the mixture was 40 ml.

Fig. 4. Curve I, 100 ml boric acid (0.416 M) titrated thermometrically by KF (6.02 M).
 Curve II, 100 ml boric acid (0.416 M) titrated by KF (4.8 M)
 Curve Ia and IIa represent 100 ml water titrated by KF (6.02 M) and (4.8 M).

The thermometric titrations of boric acid by potassium fluoride (Fig. 4), boric acid by hydrofluoric acid (Fig. 5) and potassium metaborate by hydrofluoric acid (Fig. 6) were performed with usual precautions⁵. Blank titrations against water have also been made,

Fig. 5. Curve I, 60 ml boric acid (0.07045 *M*) titrated thermometrically by HF (0.709 *M*).
 Curve II, 60 ml boric acid (0.0528 *M*) titrated by HF (0.709 *M*).
 Curve Ia, 60 ml water titrated by HF (0.709 *M*).

and after making corrections for the change in volume the differences were plotted. The boric acid or the borate solutions were taken in a plastic vessel, which was then placed inside a Dewar flask contained in a thermally insulated box. The hydrofluoric acid or the potassium fluoride were added from a polythene burette. The Beckmann thermometer was thinly coated with collodion in such a way that there was no difficulty in measuring the change in temperature of the solution. The temperature change at a constant volume has been plotted against the volume of the titrant added.

5. A. K. Sengupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **33**, 433.

Fig. 6. Curve I, 100 ml of $KBO_2 \cdot H_2O$ (0.04725 *M*) titrated thermometrically by HF (0.6009 *M*).
 Curve II, 60 ml of $KBO_2 \cdot H_2O$ (0.03937 *M*) titrated by HF (0.6009 *M*).
 Curve Ia, and IIa, 100 ml and 60 ml water titrated by HF (0.6009 *M*).

For the phase rule study (Fig. 7) of the system $KF-H_3BO_3-H_2O$ separate mixtures were made by mixing the reactants. The relative concentrations of potassium fluoride and boric acid were varied, and the volume of water was adjusted in such a manner that there always existed a solid phase in equilibrium with the liquid phase. The mixtures were made in polythene bottles. They were shaken from time to time. After a fortnight keeping at a temperature of 30° both the solid and liquid phases were taken out from each bottle, and the contents of potassium fluoride and boric acid were estimated³ respectively as calcium fluoride and by acidimetric titration in presence of mannitol.

Fig. 7. Phase rule diagram of $\text{KF-H}_3\text{BO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ system.

DISCUSSION

In the conductometric and thermometric titrations of the system $\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3\text{-KF}$ (vide, Figs. 1 and 4) inflection points have been observed at the $\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3 : \text{KF}$ ratios 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 4. These breaks may be explained through the successive formation of various fluoborate anions, viz., $\text{BF}(\text{OH})_3^-$, $\text{BF}_2(\text{OH})_2^-$, BF_3OH^- and BF_4^- . The first of these reactions may be represented as follows :

This reaction also explains the increase in the solubility of boric acid in alkali fluoride solutions.

The conductometric and thermometric titrations of H_3BO_3 by HF (vide, Figs. 2 and 5) showed two breaks at $\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3 : \text{HF}$ ratio 1 : 3 and 1 : 4. These inflection points are, most probably, due to the formation of monohydroxytrifluoroboric acid and tetrafluoroboric acid.

The conductometric and thermometric titrations of the system $\text{KBO}_2\text{-H}_2\text{O-HF}$ (vide, Figs. 3 and 6) showed breaks corresponding to the borate : acid ratio at 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 4 indicating the formation of dihydroxydifluo-, monohydroxytrifluo- and tetrafluoroborate ions through the reactions given below. Infra-red spectral studies of the above metaborate

have indicated characteristic B—OH frequency at 3400 cm^{-1} , but no band due to water molecules, and therefore, the above metaborate may be represented as $\text{KBO}(\text{OH})_2$.

The absence of the break at the 1 : 1 ratio of the above two reactants may be explained by the fact that in alkaline medium trihydroxy-monofluoborate ion is unstable and before reaching the equimolar reacting proportion the above mixture remains alkaline due to the metaborate still remaining.

The phase rule studies of the system $\text{KF}—\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3—\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have confirmed the above results. It has been observed (vide, Fig. 7) that the tie lines with higher concentration of KF converge to a particular point on the $\text{KF}—\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3$ line, where $\text{KF} : \text{H}_3\text{BO}_3$ is 1 : 1. The formation of $\text{KBF}(\text{OH})_3$ has thus been indicated. The curve ACDB represent the total phase equilibria. In the region ACD, i.e., at lower potassium fluoride concentration the formation of a complex compound has not been indicated. It may be inferred, therefore, (vide, curve DB) that the salt $\text{KBF}(\text{OH})_3$ is stable in presence of excess of the fluoride.

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